

Survey on Correlating Smells and Refactorings in Elixir

FREE AND ENLIGHTENED CONSENT

Title: Correlating Code Smells and Refactorings in the Elixir functional language

Institutions: DCC/ICEx/UFMG and DPI/CCE/UFV

Responsible researchers:

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Associate professor at the Department of Computer Science at UFMG

This "Free and Enlightened Consent" contains information about our research. If you have any questions, do not hesitate to ask the responsible researchers.

Evaluation goals: This study aims to understand developers' perspectives on the ability of refactoring strategies for Elixir to remove code smells from programs implemented in this language

Survey information: We will ask you questions about your demographics, positions held, experience with Elixir, and your perception of code smell removal using refactoring strategies in Elixir (i.e., the completeness of the removals).

Data collection and use: The data will be collected through this Google Form. It is estimated that each participant will need a maximum of 60 minutes to complete the answers. This data will be used to promote good practices to improve the quality of code implemented in Elixir. The identities of all participants, as well as their responses, will be kept confidential. You may choose to receive the preliminary results of the study, with the anonymity of data and participants preserved. The results will be published and presented at conferences and scientific journals without revealing the identity of the participants.

If you decide not to participate in the research: You are free to refuse to participate or withdraw your consent at any time. Your decision will not affect any relationship with the evaluators, professors, or the institution responsible for this research.

Compensation: Your participation is voluntary and unpaid. In addition, you will not be charged for participating in this research.

If you have any problems or any other questions about the research or the ethical aspects of this study: You can contact Lucas Vegi at any time at lucas.vegi@ufv.br.

Risks and measures to minimize them: When answering the questions, you may feel uncomfortable with questions that can bring back bad memories, fear of not knowing the answer, or even being identified. If you feel uncomfortable, you can pause completing the questionnaire and withdraw from participation at any time. The guarantee of data confidentiality ensured by the researchers is limited to the privacy policies of the virtual environment used for data collection (Google Forms). According to Brazilian legislation (Art. 9 of Resolution nº 510/16 of the National Health Council), in case of any damages resulting from your participation in this research, you will have the right to be compensated, under the terms of the Law.

Benefits: This research aims to promote good practices for improving the quality of systems implemented in Elixir, thus justifying its risks.

This survey will be carried out entirely remotely. In this way, [this consent term will be made available in digital copy through this Google Form](#). A copy of this digital consent will be kept by the responsible researchers and you will receive a digital copy via email after signing the term.

* Indica uma pergunta obrigatória

E-mail *

Seu e-mail

Your full name: *

Sua resposta

Free and Enlightened Consent (voluntary agreement) *

I declare that I have read the document mentioned above and that I agree to participate as a volunteer, authorizing the anonymous use of the data generated by my participation for the academic purposes described above.

Avançar

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Limpar formulário

Survey on Correlating Smells and Refactorings in Elixir

* Indica uma pergunta obrigatória

Demographic questions

Select your country: *

Your city: *

Elixir experience time: *

- Less than 1 year
- Between 1 and 3 years
- More than 3 years

How many different projects have you participated in using Elixir? *

- Only one project
- Between 2 and 4 projects
- More than 4 projects

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Survey on Correlating Smells and Refactorings in Elixir

* Indica uma pergunta obrigatória

Perceptions on code smell removal using refactoring strategies in Elixir

In previous studies, we cataloged [35 code smells](#) and [82 refactorings](#) tailored for Elixir. **In the present work, we are proposing practical guidelines for removing code smells in Elixir using sequences of refactorings specific to the language.**

For each code smell you are asked to evaluate, we will present the refactorings useful for its removal and explain their specific applications. These refactorings are listed in the order in which they should be performed when they are part of a sequence of operations. Specifically, when a refactoring should be applied on its own, it is listed with a bullet point (i.e., •). Conversely, when a refactoring is part of a sequence of operations, it is numbered to indicate its order (e.g., 1., 2., etc.).

Therefore, based on your experience, please answer the following questions for each presented smell:

Do you agree that this sequence of refactorings removes this smell?

- Please rate the degree to which the refactoring sequence removes the code smell
- (1 = the refactoring sequence absolutely does not help remove the smell; 5 = the refactoring sequence completely removes the smell)

Notes:

- Each smell and refactoring is accompanied by a short description and a link with code examples.

Do you agree that this sequence of refactorings remove the [\[Feature Envy\]](#) smell? *

This smell occurs when a function accesses more data or calls more functions from another module than from its own. The presence of this smell can make a module less cohesive and increase code coupling. To remove this smell, we apply the following refactorings:

1. [\[Extract function\]](#): If part of a function calls more functions from other modules than from the module where it is defined, we can use this refactoring to separate the envious part into a new function.
 2. [\[Moving a definition\]](#): If a function calls more functions from other modules than from the module where it is defined (e.g., the function extracted in the previous refactoring), we can move it to the module most accessed by it.
- [\[Remove import attributes\]](#): By using this refactoring, we can directly identify the origin of a function being called by another function. This way, we can more clearly identify a *Feature envy* instance, helping us to subsequently remove it.

(1 = absolutely does not remove the smell; 5 = completely removes the smell)

	1	2	3	4	5
Removal	<input type="radio"/>				

Please justify your answer, especially if you rated it below 4 for the previous smell:

Sua resposta _____

Do you agree that this sequence of refactorings remove the [\[Large code generation by macros\]](#) smell? *

This code smell is related to macros that generate too much code. When a macro provides a large code generation, it impacts how the compiler or the runtime works. The reason for this is that Elixir may have to expand, compile, and execute a code multiple times, which will make compilation slower. To remove this smell, we apply the following refactorings:

1. [\[Extract function\]](#): When we have a *macro* that generates a large volume of code, potentially compromising compiler performance, we can use this refactoring to extract part of the *macro*'s code and encapsulate it in a conventional function that the *macro* will call. This approach reduces the amount of code that is expanded and compiled with each invocation of the *macro*.
2. [\[Moving a definition\]](#): After extracting the function, it may eventually be necessary to move it to another module to make the code more cohesive.

(1 = absolutely does not remove the smell; 5 = completely removes the smell)

	1	2	3	4	5
Removal	<input type="radio"/>				

Please justify your answer, especially if you rated it below 4 for the previous smell:

Sua resposta _____

Do you agree that this sequence of refactorings remove the [\[Unsupervised process\]](#) smell? *

This smell occurs when a library creates processes outside a supervision tree, therefore not allowing users to control their apps fully. To remove this smell, we apply the following refactorings:

- [\[Moving error-handling mechanisms to supervision trees\]](#): Regardless of whether error-handling mechanisms are used or not, an unsupervised process can be moved to a supervision tree using this refactoring. With this transformation, the initialization of processes is delegated to a *Supervisor* and is no longer performed directly by the clients. This refactoring allows you to choose which module that behaves as a *Supervisor* to move to, or even to create a new module that implements the *Application* behaviour to act as a supervision tree.
- [\[Moving a definition\]](#): We can move the process initialization function calls (e.g., `GenServer.start/3`) into a *Supervisor*, delegating this task to it.

(1 = absolutely does not remove the smell; 5 = completely removes the smell)

	1	2	3	4	5
Removal	<input type="radio"/>				

Please justify your answer, especially if you rated it below 4 for the previous smell:

Sua resposta _____

Do you agree that this sequence of refactorings remove the [\[Alternative return types\]](#) smell? *

This code smell refers to functions that receive options (e.g., *keyword list*) parameters that drastically change its return type. Because options are optional and sometimes set dynamically, if they change the return type it may be hard to understand what the function actually returns. To remove this smell, we apply the following refactorings:

1. [\[Introduce a temporary duplicate definition\]](#): When a function receives a *Keyword list* as a parameter, which can drastically change its return type depending on its contents, we should initially use this refactoring to create a copy of the original function for each different return type.
2. [\[Rename an identifier\]](#): After creating the copies, we should rename each one according to its respective return type. Additionally, the bodies of the copies should be modified to fit the specific return types.
3. [\[Add or remove a parameter\]](#): At this point in the refactoring process, since the *Keyword list* parameter is no longer necessary in any of the renamed copies of the original function, we can use this operation to remove the unnecessary parameter.
4. [\[Typing parameters and return values\]](#): Finally, we can use this operation on each of the functions involved in this composite refactoring to document their interfaces.
5. [\[Remove dead code\]](#): This refactoring can be used on the copies of the functions created previously in this sequence of transformations to clean up their bodies, removing unused code.

(1 = absolutely does not remove the smell; 5 = completely removes the smell)

	1	2	3	4	5
Removal	<input type="radio"/>				

Please justify your answer, especially if you rated it below 4 for the previous smell:

Sua resposta

Do you agree that this sequence of refactorings remove the [\[Comments\]](#) smell? *

This smell occurs when a function is documented using explanatory comments instead of `@doc`, or when comments are used to compensate for poorly written code. To remove this smell, we apply the following refactorings:

- [\[Extract function\]](#): If a comment explains a block of code, that block can be extracted into a separate function. The name of the new function can often be derived from the comment itself.
- [\[Extract expressions\]](#): If a comment is intended to explain a complex expression, the expression should be split into understandable sub-expressions using this refactoring.
- [\[Extract constant\]](#): If a comment is used to explain magic numbers, this refactoring can replace the comments with constants that have human-friendly names.
- [\[Rename an identifier\]](#): If a function, expression, or constant has already been extracted, but comments are still necessary to explain what they do, give a self-explanatory name to them using this operation.
- [\[Typing parameters and return values\]](#): If a comment is used to document the types of a function's parameters or the type of its return value, that comment can be replaced by a function specification using the `@spec` module attribute.
- [\[Add type declarations and contracts\]](#): Alternatively, if a comment is used to document data structures received as parameters of a function or even returned by a function, this comment can be replaced by a type specification using the `@type` and `@typedoc` module attributes.

(1 = absolutely does not remove the smell; 5 = completely removes the smell)

	1	2	3	4	5
Removal	<input type="radio"/>				

Please justify your answer, especially if you rated it below 4 for the previous smell:

Sua resposta

Do you agree that this sequence of refactorings remove the [\[GenServer envy\]](#) smell? *

This smell occurs when a `Task` or `Agent` is used but handled as if it were a `GenServer`. To remove this smell, we apply the following refactorings:

1. [\[Generalise a process abstraction\]](#): When an `Agent` or `Task` goes beyond its suggested use cases and becomes painful, it is better to refactor it into a `GenServer` using this operation.
2. [\[Introduce processes\]](#): When we finish generalizing a process, it may still be insufficient to achieve an optimal mapping with the parallel activities of the problem being solved. In these circumstances, we can use this refactoring to remove bottlenecks.
3. [\[Register a process\]](#): When we create a new process, we can also use this refactoring to assign a user-defined name to the new process ID and use that user-defined name instead of the process ID in message passing.
4. [\[Remove dead code\]](#): When we are generalizing a process `Agent` or `Task` into a `GenServer`, naturally, some functions of the module that represented the original process may become useless and can therefore be removed.

(1 = absolutely does not remove the smell; 5 = completely removes the smell)

	1	2	3	4	5
Removal	<input type="radio"/>				

Please justify your answer, especially if you rated it below 4 for the previous smell:

Sua resposta

Do you agree that this sequence of refactorings remove the **[Duplicated Code]** smell? *

This smell occurs when two or more code fragments look almost identical. Duplicated code can cause maintenance issues especially when changes are needed. Since multiple code fragments will have to be updated, there is the risk that one of them will not be changed, causing unwanted system behavior. To remove this smell, we apply the following refactorings:

- **[Defining a subset of a Map]:** It can be used to eliminate duplicated code generated by the manual access of values when extracting part of a Map
 - **[Modifying keys in a Map]:** This refactoring can be used to eliminate duplicated code generated by the manual process of replacing a name given to a Map key.
 - **[Folding against a function definition]:** When code contains expressions that perform operations already implemented in existing functions, we can remove this code duplication by using this refactoring, thus replacing the own expressions with calls to the existing functions.
 - **[Extract expressions]:** When the same expression is repeated multiple times within a function, we can assign the expression to a variable and reuse that variable in all parts where the result of the expression is needed.
 - **[Extract function]:** When the same code block appears in two different functions, we can extract it to a new function and call this function from both places where the code was originally duplicated.
 - **[Reducing a boolean equality expression]:** When dealing with a boolean expression consisting of multiple equality comparisons involving the same variable and logical OR operators, we can eliminate duplicated code using this refactoring, thus utilizing the IN operator and a list containing all possible valid values for the variable.
 - **[Generalise a function definition]:** When we have different functions that have non-identical but equivalent expressions, we can use this refactoring to create a new higher-order function that generalizes the equivalent expressions and subsequently is called in places where the expressions were originally used.
 - **[Turning anonymous into local functions]:** When we encounter the same anonymous function being defined in different points of the codebase, these anonymous functions should be transformed into a local function, and the locations where the anonymous functions were originally implemented should be updated to use the new local function.
 - **[Merging multiple definitions]:** There are situations where a codebase may have distinct and complementary functions. Because they are complementary, these functions may have identical code snippets. When identified, these functions can be merged into a new function that will simultaneously perform the processing done by the original functions separately.
 - **[Move expression out of case]:** When the same expression is repeated at the end of all branches of a case statement, this refactoring can be used to eliminate the duplicated code.
 - **[Remove redundant last clause in "with"]:** When the last clause of a with statement is composed of a pattern identical to the predefined value to be returned by the with in case all checked patterns match, this clause is considered redundant. Therefore this duplicated code can be eliminated using this refactoring.
 - **[Static structure reuse]:** When identical tuples or lists are used at different points within a function, they are unnecessarily recreated by Elixir. Use this refactoring to eliminate these redundant recreations by assigning the structures to variables, allowing them to be shared throughout the code.
 - **[Introduce import]:** When a module A calls many functions from a module B, the name of module B may appear repetitively in the code of module A due to fully-qualified name calls. This type of duplicated code can be eliminated by importing module B into module A.
 - **[Widen or narrow definition scope]:** When we encounter the same anonymous function defined in different parts of the codebase, these functions should be transformed into a local function, eliminating code duplication by expanding the scope of the original function. This refactoring serves as an alternative to *[Turning anonymous into local functions]*.
1. **[Introduce Enum.map/2]:** When each element of a list is manually generated by repeatedly calling the same function, we can use this refactoring to eliminate duplicated code and make the code more idiomatic.
 2. **[Transform to list comprehension]:** Optionally, after using the previous refactoring to eliminate duplicated code, we can use this operation to convert the call to Enum.map/2 into semantically equivalent code that can be also more declarative and easier to read.
 3. **[List comprehension simplifications]:** Optionally, after using the previous refactoring as part of a sequence of atomic refactorings to eliminate duplicated code, we can also use this refactoring to revert the previous transformation, thereby retaining calls to the higher-order function Enum.map/2 instead of using list comprehensions.

(1 = absolutely does not remove the smell; 5 = completely removes the smell)

	1	2	3	4	5
Removal	<input type="radio"/>				

Please justify your answer, especially if you rated it below 4 for the previous smell:

Sua resposta

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[Avançar](#)

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Final remarks

Please add here any comment about our work and survey:

Sua resposta

Do you want to receive the preliminary results of this study? *

- Yes
- No

Uma cópia das suas respostas será enviada para o endereço de e-mail fornecido

[Voltar](#)

[Enviar](#)

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